

STRATEGIC LEADERSHIP AND STRATEGIC PLAN: THEIR INFLUENCES ON STRATEGIC POLICY AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN A COMPANY

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze and explain the effect of strategic leadership and strategic planning on employee performance mediated by strategic policies and moderated by technological capabilities. The method used in this study is a quantitative approach with data analysis techniques using SmartPLS (Part Least Square). Data was collected by distributing questionnaires to 99 PT Pacto and PT Royalindo. The results show that strategic leadership is proven to be directly able to improve employee performance and strategic planning, but strategic planning cannot improve employee performance. Likewise, strategic policies have improved employee performance and strategic planning but are not related to employee performance. This study also found that strategic planning does not act as mediation in improving performance, but technological capabilities can improve employee performance and strengthen the performance of employees who are driven by the strategic leadership.

Keywords: Strategic leadership, strategic plan, strategic policy, technological capability and employee performance.

INTRODUCTION

This study highlights the performance of employees, which is suspected by the decline in the number of tourists to tourist destinations in Jakarta- Indonesia. In this era of globalization, good performance by employees is essential for companies (Hammoud & Nash, 2014). Various essential and strategic efforts that are scheduled to optimize performance are highly dependent on the willingness and determination to become a successful person with optimal performance (Rohrbeck et al., 2015). Vera & Crossan (2004) stated that the factors that influence performance include strategic leadership, strategic plans and strategic policies. Strategic planning is the latest paradigm characterized by applying the principles of transparency and understanding the use of information technology (Bryson et al., 2018); Tavakoli et al., 2015).

Strategic plans play an essential role in improving performance (Amrollahi et al., 2014). Formal strategic planning methods have been studied and developed in recent years, and from a theoretical point of view, strategic planning leads to the development of better performance (Wolf & Floyd, 2017). Many studies linking strategic leadership with performance have been carried out, including (Dhurkari & Nandakumar, 2015); (Koohang & Hatch, 2017); Lichtenthaler & Fischbach, 2018);(Jamil Anwar, SAF Hasnu, 2017); (Altman & Tushman, 2017);(Lindquist & Marcy, 2016); Viitala et al., 2020) but the results are pretty mixed. Some state that strategic leadership affects performance, including Altman & Tushman (2017);

Koohang & Hatch (2017); Lichtenthaler & Fischbach, (2016); Lindquist & Marcy, (2016) but some state that strategic leadership does not affect performance, including Viitala et al., (2020); Jamil Anwar, SAF Hasnu, 2017; Dhurkari & Nandakumar, (2015). Based on Table 1.2 above, the results of previous researchers showed inconsistencies. Thus, attracting researchers to uncover these gaps. The relationship between leadership and employee performance refers to the opinion (Yukl, 2008) that the leader certainly influences his subordinates, meaning that the leader acts as a credible and attractive role model because he has the authority to punish and reward.

Strategic leadership always prioritizes the management system in managing its activities (Kalangi et al., 2021; Sari et al., 2021). Every activity to improve its performance always begins with a strategic policy that is carried out with a priority scale. Between leadership and policy can simultaneously improve employee performance. Koohang & Hatch, 2017 revealed that strategic leadership could improve company performance, while Agostini & Wegner (2018) stated that strategic policy significantly affects company performance. Leadership and policies always begin with careful and strategic planning to maintain the company's position when the situation is changing so fast. Therefore, the researchers included the strategic planning variable as a mediating variable which, in the end, the strategic plan was able to improve the company's performance (Donkor et al., 2018; (Kariuki et al., 2017).

Along with the phenomena that occur, the Industry is expected to prepare and anticipate changes that will occur in the implementation of MICE in the future where there will be a shift from offline to online or a combination of online and offline activities. Virtual events expand potential audiences and build new revenue sources. The increase in online meetings and the development of technology capabilities make virtual events abreast of uncertain situations (Ziyoda, 2020).

This study begins with a phenomenon that appears that the performance of MICE businesses in Indonesia, especially in DKI Jakarta, has not been maximized, so tourist visits have decreased. According to Khajeh, (2018), the factors that influence performance include strategic leadership. Strategic leadership is an effort to control organizational members to follow organizational standards and goals (Sakarina, 2021). Strategic policies, in the form of the organization's vision and mission and human resources, are related to employees' quality to work optimally (Sellers, 2017). Therefore, in this study, strategic leadership becomes the independent variable. After reviewing the literature on the use of strategic leadership associated with employee performance, it turns out that it is inconsistent; that is, some have an effect, and some do not. To solve the gap between strategic leadership and employee performance, the technology capability variable is used as a moderating variable for reasons along with the times and the environment due to the uncertainty of when the pandemic will end. The MICE industry inevitably has to adapt and be ready to anticipate changes in the implementation of MICE in the future by a shift from offline to online or a combination of online and offline activities. Virtual events expand potential audiences and build new revenue sources. In addition, it encourages stimulating the domestic market first to start carrying out MICE activities in Jakarta destinations. Palladan et al (2016) emphasizes that the

development of technological capabilities moderates strategic leadership in improving performance. Meanwhile, Abbas et al. (2014) research states that technology capability has a significant effect on employee performance. Referring to the two research results, the placement of the technological capacity variable as a moderating variable is an exclusive variable, which means that it can strengthen the influence of strategic leadership on company performance and improve company performance.

In addition, the technological capability variable is used as a novelty variable because MICE companies must adopt new technologies to build and maintain their strategic aspects. In this pandemic situation, the use of technology is significant. Technological variables associated with company performance are still rarely done by previous researchers. This can be proven from the results of the meta-analysis of Heine et al. (2003), which states that technology research is associated with company performance from 1993 to 2001, including Kelley M et al. (1994); Goodhue D et al. (1995); Malhotra MK et al., (2001) and Das A et al., (2001) while Liu, P. et al., (2013) identified researchers as the relationship between technology capability and firm performance including Bhatta G.D. et al.,(2005); Patracosol B et al., (2009); Santhanam & Hartono, (2003).

As for the consideration of the place where this research was carried out in Jakarta because of the many access to facilities and infrastructure, adequate infrastructure for MICE activities such as the number of international flight airports to and from destinations, having a destination Marketing Organization such as the Convention Bureau, the availability of restaurants, bars, theaters, night clubs, malls, the availability of buildings with unique architecture, monuments, tourist attractions, the number of star and non-star hotel rooms and conference venues in each star hotel, however, so far, DKI Jakarta has, in reality, been unable to compete with other cities both in Indonesia and cities in Asia. Therefore, this phenomenon is why researchers conduct further research in Jakarta.

LITERATUR REVIEW:

1. Strategic Leadership on employee performance:

Hughes and Beatty (2005) that the focus of strategic leadership is the organization's "sustainable competitive advantages" to encourage and mobilize all employee capabilities to develop. Strategic leadership is the capacity and capability of a responsible person and has an important influence on improving performance. This was confirmed by other researchers such as M.K. Nandakumar (2016); Jamil Anwar (2017); Elizabeth J. Altman (2017); Alex Koohang (2017); Philipp Wolfgang Lichtenthaler (2016), which states that strategic leadership affects employee performance. The hypothesis is built as follows:

H1: Strategic Leadership has a significant effect on employee performance.

2. Strategic leadership towards strategic plans:

Yukl (2010), in his empirical findings, states that there are several behavioural characteristics of strategic leaders, namely 1) daring to take decisive action, especially when facing a crisis,

2) having the competence to make lasting changes, 3) knowing what to do and being able to control events/situations, 4) appreciate good performance but do not blame external conditions for poor performance. Strategic leadership through strategic management with stages in formulating and producing strategies can produce appropriate strategies to be used as strategic policies that are realized into programs to run or manage resources optimally. Researcher Antigoni conducted empirical research on strategic leadership related to strategic policy (2014), Tobias K et al. (2011); Jacob Donkor et al. (2018); Peter Geoffrey et al. (2016). The hypothesis is as follows:

H2: Strategic leadership influences strategic plans.

3. Strategic policy on strategic planning:

According to Handoko (2008), the strategic policy approach to strategic planning determines a series of decisions and activities in the formulation and implementation of strategies designed to achieve organizational goals. The steps of the strategic preparation process determine the mission and goals, which include general questions about the mission, philosophy of purpose, and organizational goals. The results of empirical research prove that strategic policies are related to strategic planning (Alicia Ohlsson 2014; Meywati et al., 2021).

H3: Strategic policies have a significant effect on strategic plans.

4. Strategic policies on employee performance:

The selection of alternative strategic actions as the best choice of action is not the end of the formulation or formulation of strategies. However, then the organization must develop additional policies. Policies are generally used as general guidelines on strategy implementation. Policies can also limit the choice of strategy in the future so that a change must follow a change in strategy in the policy. Based on the opinion of Aizawa Kakeru (2012), the policy is a written rule which is a formal decision of the organization, which is binding, which regulates behaviour intending to create new values in the organization. The results of previous studies show that strategic policies affect employee performance, such as Mizutani and Nakamura (2014), Goldstein and Iossifova (2012), Pitelis (2007). Then the hypothesis that is built is:

H4: Strategic policies have a significant effect on employee performance.

5. Strategic planning on employee performance:

Strategic planning provides consistent guidelines for the company's activities. Using strategic planning, a manager provides his organization with clearly defined goals and ways to achieve them. In addition, the process of planning helps managers anticipate problems before they arise and resolve them before they get worse. Strategic planning helps managers see opportunities that contain risks and opportunities that are safe and choose one of the opportunities that exist. The careful analysis carried out by strategic planning gives managers more information needed to make the right decisions. (Stoner 2006). Coulter (2004) suggests that a strategic plan is a plan that applies to the organization as a whole becomes the general

goal of the organization in trying to place the organization into its environment. A plan that details how to achieve the overall goal is called an operational plan. Strategic plans tend to cover a longer time frame for performing well. The results of previous studies state that strategic plans affect employee performance (Mizutani and Nakamura, (2014); Goldstein and Iossifova, (2012); Pitelis, (2007)). Thus the hypothesis is built as follows:

H5: Strategic planning has a significant effect on employee performance.

6. Planning mediates strategic leadership on performance:

Policies will be the primary reference for members to behave. Policies are generally problem-solving and proactive. Policies are more adaptive and interpretative, although policies also regulate “what is allowed, and what is not”. Policies are also expected to be general but without losing specific local characteristics. Policies must provide opportunities to be interpreted according to the specific conditions (William N. Dunn, 1999; Aryateja et al., 2021). Rita Viitala’s research (2015) shows that strategic policies are the solution for leaders to improve performance. Meanwhile, Trong Tuan Luu (2015) shows that strategic policies are a policy solution in improving employee performance. The hypothesis:

H6: Strategic planning mediates strategic leadership on employee performance.

H7: Strategic planning mediates strategic policies on employee performance.

7. Technology capability as a moderator of strategic leadership on employee performance:

In order to provide empirical evidence related to the capabilities of this information technology, researchers have made many efforts. Efforts to link information technology capabilities with a competitive advantage or company performance have been started since the 1980s (for example, research conducted by Cron and Sobol, 1983; Clemons, 1986; and Kaplan, 1989) and is continuing today (as an example of research conducted by Turulja & Bajgoric (2016) and Saunders & Brynjolfsson (2016), those who state that technological capability has strengthened leadership on employee performance include: Palladan, Ahmad & Abdulkadir, Kadzrina & Chong, Yen (2016)). The hypothesis:

H8. Technology capability moderates the influence of strategic leadership on firm performance.

RESEARCH METHOD

1. Research Design:

This research is explanatory research, which explains the causal relationship between variables and their effects through hypothesis testing (Sekaran, 2003). In this study, strategic leadership and strategic policy are independent variables, hereinafter referred to as exogenous variables, employee performance variables as dependent variables, hereinafter referred to as endogenous variables, strategic planning variables as mediating variables and technology capability as moderating variables. This research paradigm uses a positivism approach,

namely quantitative methods. The quantitative approach is intended to explain the relationship between research variables through hypothesis testing, and in general, the data is presented in numbers calculated through statistical tests.

1) Population and Sample:

The population of this research is all employees of PT Royalindo and PT Pacto, totalling 100 people consisting of 40 employees of P.T. Royalindo and 59 employees of P.T. Pacto convex. So a total of 99 people. Sampling for research according to Suharsimi Arikunto (2010:112), if the subject is less than 100 people, all of them should be taken as samples. The sampling technique uses saturated samples. Saturated sampling is a sampling technique when all population members are used as samples (Sekaran, 2016). It can be explained that the sampling of 99 people according to the researcher is sufficient to represent the total population of employees. Hair et al. (2013) revealed that the research sample is part of the population to be studied and is considered representative of the population; PLS-SEM does not demand a large number of samples. Minimum recommended between 30 to 100 data. According to Ghozali (2015), the number of PLS samples can be calculated by ten (10) times the endogenous variables in the model.

2) Research Hypothesis Testing:

Hypothesis testing is done by resampling Bootstrap developed by Geisser & Stone. The statistical test used is a t-test with a critical number of t-statistics greater than t-table (1,96) with a significance level of 0.05, then the hypothesis testing is accepted. Otherwise, the t-statistic is smaller than the t-table (1, 96). Hypothesis testing is not accepted. Hypothesis testing on the outer model is significant; this indicates that the indicator can be used as an instrument for measuring latent variables, whereas if the test results on the inner model are significant, there is a significant effect between one latent variable another (Solimun). , 2011).

3) Analysis of mediating variables:

The analysis of the mediating variable can be done through two approaches, namely, the difference in coefficients and the multiplication of the coefficients. The coefficient difference approach uses an examination method by analyzing with and without involving mediating variables. The method of examination is by doing two analyzes, namely analysis involving mediating variables and analysis without involving mediating variables. This study examines the intervention of the mediating variable, whether it is proven to act as a complete mediation variable or as a partial mediation and not as a mediating variable.

4) Analysis of moderating variables:

Sugiono (2013) defines the moderating variable, namely: "Variables that affect (strengthen and weaken) the relationship between the independent and dependent variables." The analysis of the moderating variable in this study was used to test whether technology capability could strengthen the influence of strategic leadership on employee performance. Moderation is done by multiplying the capability variable with the strategic leadership variable.

RESULTS

Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

No	Description	%
Sex		
1	Male	70
2	Female	30
	Total.	100
Respondent Age		
1	Less than 30 years	79
2	30 years – 40 years	21
	Total.	100
Level of education		
1	Senior High School	15
2	Diploma	15
3	Bachelor	65
4	Master	5
	Total.	100
Years of service		
1	Less than two years	23
2	Two years - 4 years	32
3	Four years - 5 years	39
4	More than five years	16
	Total.	100

Source: Primary Data Processed,2020

Table 1 shows that 70 per cent of male respondents and 30 per cent of female respondents. It can be explained why male employees dominate respondents because these two companies, PT Pacto and PT Royalindo, operationally require extra hard work day and night for a successful event. Hard work requires strong physical endurance; this is only owned by men, while women are only administrative to support operations, as stated by Pulkkinen et al. (1999) regarding gender characteristics between men and women. This shows that career orientation is explained by personality characteristics that show high self-control over compliance emotions. Social activity is related to women's career orientation but not to men. Passivity in work is a risk factor for women but not for career orientation for men. Gender differences are emphasized in terms of career stability: Stable and unstable careers are more closely related to the personality characteristics of women than men. Each respondent, both male and female, is dominated by a bachelor's education level and productive age between approximately 30 years as much as 79 per cent and those aged less than 40 years as much as 21 per cent. Regarding the level of undergraduate education, which is more dominant, it is true that companies engaged in organizing this national event require adequate scientific and intellectual insight because they are dealing with foreign guests who conduct conference

activities so that they can adjust to the event. The majority of respondents are less than 30 years old, i.e. 79 per cent, and 21 per cent of respondents are 30 to 40 years old. The explanation why employees aged less than 30 years are more dominant because that age is needed to deal with challenging work so that they require reliable and skilled workers at work and have been trained before working, as the results of research from Bhargava R. Kotur (2014) how the age factor and gender affect the level of performance of workers in the company. Workers in the middle age range perform better at less than 30 years of age. Gender was also found to affect performance, and female workers were relatively more productive in administration. Likewise, these young people who have been trained are very productive, and so far, it has been proven that they have carried out their duties well so that the implementation of the event has no complaints from clients.

Twenty-one per cent is more than 30 years old to 40 years old. Although they are few, they have experience in the service sector to support younger employees in terms of providing services. Employees' most extended working period is more than five years by 16 per cent. This age is productive to become the company's mainstay in carrying out operational tasks. This indicates that the employee is experienced and feels comfortable working. His position is as a coordinator and supervision of young employees, and he has less than two years of experience. Most employees who have a working period of fewer than two years do not have sufficient experience in the service sector. They are generally new employees, namely employees under the age of 30. They work while learning to prepare techniques to conduct events both nationally and internationally.

Validity test:

Validity is a measure that shows the level of validity or validity. The principle of validity is a measurement or observation, which means the reliability of the instrument in collecting data. The instrument must be able to measure what it is supposed to measure. So validity emphasizes measurement or observation tools, while reliability is the similarity of measurement or observation results if the facts or reality were measured or observed many times at different times. Tools and methods of measuring or observing both play an essential role simultaneously. Testing the validity of reflective indicators uses the correlation between item scores and construct scores. Measurements with reflective indicators show a change in one indicator in a construct if other indicators in the exact construct change. Reflective indicators are suitable for measuring perception, so this study uses reflective indicators. The indicators used in this study are declared valid or have met convergent validity.

Table 2. Validity and Reliability Test Results

Variable		Indicator	Loading factor	Note
Strategic leadership	X1.1	Leaders always think ahead.	0.871	Valid
	X1.2	Leaders can describe challenges and opportunities.	0.881	
	X1.3	Leaders always encourage subordinates to stay active	0.919	
	X1.4	Leaders always hold training for their subordinates	0.809	
	X1.5	Leaders always transfer knowledge	0.891	
	X1.6	Leaders have information technology skills.	0.906	
	X1.7	Leaders can utilize human resources	0.885	
	X1.8	Leaders direct their subordinates to be competitive	0.929	
	X1.9	.Leadership always imitates subordinates with behaviour	0.940	
	X1.10	The leader always gives directions every Monday morning.	0.915	
	X1.11	Leaders always build good relations with subordinates and relationships.	0.761	
Strategic policy	X2.1	Leaders always prioritize change for the better.	0.892	Valid
	X2.2	Leaders always suggest new products.	0.894	
	X2.3	Leaders always think positive and are customer-focused	0.799	
	X2.4	Leaders are honest and open	0.898	
	X2.5	Leaders always build mutual trust	0,880	
	X2.6	Leaders are consistent between speech and behaviour.	0,807	
	X2.7	The leader always responds quickly to the complaints of his subordinates	0.901	
	X2.8	Leaders always provide solutions to problems	0.917	
Strategic planning	Y1.1	Leaders have long-term plans.	0.937	Valid
	Y1.2	Leaders always think about the success of the company	0.947	
	Y1.3	Leaders always direct subordinates to be influential.	0.927	
	Y1.4	Leaders are always practical and efficient at work	0.796	
	Y1.5	Leaders always give rewards to subordinates	0.904	
	Y1.6	Leaders are good at lobbying.	0.938	
Technology Capability	Y2.1	I work always using the internet.	0.900	Vald
	Y2.2	I can become an internet operator	0.844	
	Y2.3	I always combine the service system online / offline.	0.896	
	Y2.4	I have known many subscribers joined social media	0.923	

	Y2.5	I'm always looking for new customers on the internet app	0.922	Valid
	Y2.6	I always focus on the customer on the Internet	0.772	
	Y2.7	I always develop new products in online business	0.903	
	Y2.8	I always take advantage of new opportunities in online business	0.908	
Employee performance	Y3.1	I generate a lot of new customers.	0,919	
	Y3.2	I have generated a lot of followers on social media.	0.867	
	Y3.3	My work is quite good.	0.906	
	Y3.4	The results of my work can satisfy customers.	0.923	
	Y3.5	I work according to the set time	0.928	
	Y3.6	I am always consistent with my promises	0.753	

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2020

Reliability Test:

A reliability test is used to determine whether the research instrument used can be used many times at different times (Ferdinand, 2006). The instrument can be said to be reliable if the Cronbach's Alpha value is 0.6 or more (Sugiyono, 2003). The results of the research instrument reliability test, with the Smart PLS program as follows for each latent variable, are presented in Table 3 below

Table 3 Reliability Test Results

Variable	Alpha Cronbach	AVE	Composite Reliability	Note
KAPABILITAS TEKNOLOGI	0,960	0,783	0,966	Reliable
KEBIJAKAN STRATEGIES	0,956	0,765	0,963	Reliable
KEPEMIMPINAN STRATEGIS	0,972	0,781	0,975	Reliable
KINERJA KARYAWAN	0.943	0,783	0.956	Reliable
PERENCANAAN STRATEGIS	0,958	0,827	0,966	Reliable
MODERATING EFFECT	1.000	1.000	1.000	Reliable

Source: Primary data, processed (2021)

Conformity Test and Statistical Test:

The goodness of the Fit Structural model is measured using FIT, which is equivalent to R-Square in regression analysis or the coefficient of total determination in path analysis or Q². FIT shows the total variance of all variables that can be explained by the structural model. The FIT value ranges from 0 to 1. The larger this value, the greater the proportion of variable variance that the model can explain. If the FIT value = 1 means that the model can perfectly explain the phenomenon being investigated. The following is Table 4 Goodness of fit in this study.

Table4 R Square Value

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Employee Performance	0,990	0,990
Strategic Planning	0,971	0,970

Source: Data processed 2021

Path Coefficient Estimation:

The estimated value of the path coefficient between the constructs must have a significant value. The significance of the relationship can be obtained by Bootstrapping or Jackknifing procedures. The resulting value is a t-count value which is then compared with a t-table. If the t-count > t-table (1.96) at the significance level (5%), then the estimated path coefficient value is significant.

Table 5: Direct Effect

	Original sample (O)	T. Statistics	P Values	Note
Strategic Leadership → Employee Performance	0,681	2.015	0,044	Significant
Strategic leadership → Strategic planning.	0,411	17.824	0.000	Significant
Strategic policy → Employee Performance	0,543	2.424	0.016	Significant
Strategic policy → Strategic planning.	0,446	5.483	0,000	Significant
Strategic planning → Employee Performance.	0.404	1.158	0.247	Not Significant
Technology Capability → Employee Performance	0,771	3.294	0.001	Significant
Moderating effect → Employee performance	0.014	2.378	0.018	Significant

Source: 2020 data processing results.

Table 5 above shows that the relationship between strategic leadership and employee performance gives the 2015 t-statistic value greater than the predetermined standard (1.96). The original sample estimate value is 0.044, which means it has an effect (P.value 0.044). Thus the hypothesis that has been built is that strategic leadership has a significant effect on employee performance. Furthermore, the relationship between strategic leadership and strategic planning is significant, with a t statistic of 17,824, which is greater than the standard of 1.96. The original sample estimate value is 0.411, and the p value is 0.000, which indicates that the direction of the relationship between strategic leadership and strategic planning is

positive. Thus the hypothesis (H2) in this study is accepted.

The table above shows that strategic policies are associated with positive employee performance with a t statistic of 2.424, which means more than the standard value (1.96). The original sample estimate value is 0.543, which means it has a significant effect. Thus the hypothesis that has been built is that strategic policy has a significant effect on employee performance in this study is accepted. Likewise, the relationship between strategic policy and strategic planning in the table above shows that the two variables show a significant positive with a t statistic of 17,824. This value has a value much greater than the standard 1.96. The sample t value is 0.446, and the p value is 0.000, which means that it is significantly positive. Thus the hypothesis that has been built in this study that strategic policy has a significant effect on strategic planning has been accepted.

In the table above, it is also stated that strategic planning related to employee performance shows the t-statistical value of 1.158, which is smaller than the standard 1.96. The p-value is 0.247, which means it is not significant. The hypothesis that has been built is that strategic planning has a significant effect on employee performance. Thus the hypothesis can be rejected. The table above shows that technology capability is associated with employee performance greater than the standard 1.96. The sample t value is 0.771, and the p value is 0.001, which means it is significant. Moderating effect on employee performance, the t statistic is 2,378, which is greater than the standard 1.96, meaning that the p-value is 0.018, which is significant. The hypothesis that has been built is that technological capability moderates the effect of organizational commitment on employee performance. The hypothesis is accepted.

Table 6: Indirect effect

	t statistic	Standard	Note
Strategic leadership → Strategic Planning → Employee Performance	1.197	1.96	Tidak Signifikan
Strategic policy → Strategic Planning → Employee Performance	1.139	1.96	Tidak Signifikan

Source: Research results processed 2021

Based on Table 6 shows that the indirect effect of strategic leadership on employee performance through strategic planning is 1,197, not significant, while strategic policy style and performance through strategic planning has a value of 1,139, which is smaller than 1.96, meaning that it is not significant.

Discussion

1) The influence of strategic leadership on employee performance:

The results of the study indicate that strategic leadership has a significant effect on employee performance. The results of this study have similarities with the results of previous studies,

namely M.K. Nandakumar (2016); Jamil Anwar (2017); Elizabeth J. Altman (2017); Alex Koohang (2017); Philipp Wolfgang Lichtenthaler (2016), which states that strategic leadership affects employee performance. The leadership reflected in the 11 indicators has received validity from the respondents. The validity of these 11 indicators indicates that respondents have high hopes that strategic leadership will be able to explain what they expect. The most dominant indicator in reflecting the strategic leadership variable is “The leader always imitates his subordinates with behaviour” with a factor weight of 0.940 or 94 per cent, meaning that respondents consider that their superiors are role models for them because they have given many examples in their work to be successful and able to contribute to the company. Employees have hopes of doing a better job because there is always inspiration from superiors on how to do a good job, and it turns out that the employee’s expectations are realized with an average value of 4.31. The average value is said to be good because most of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed.

The lowest indicator in the strategic leadership variable is “The leader always maintains good relations with subordinates”, with a factor weight of 0.761 or 76 per cent. This perception indicates that respondents tend to expect leaders who can communicate with subordinates, even though it is the smallest among other values. In fact, the respondent’s level of agreement is quite good, and this is evident from the average value of 4.10, which is above the number four. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has forced companies to make changes in the way they do business. This is where a leader with a strategic leadership style is needed. Problems cannot be solved easily. These issues have a variety of causes that are so complex that the solution is also unpredictable. So, it takes the right leader in making decisions.

The results of hypothesis testing indicate that strategic leadership has a significant effect on strategic planning. These results support the research conducted by Antigoni (2014), Tobias K et al. (2011), Jacob Donkor et al. (2018), Peter Geoffrey et al. (2016), who concluded that strategic leadership is related to strategic planning. Almost every organization in any industry needs at least one strategic leadership figure. In most large-scale organizations, strategic leadership positions are usually occupied by top-level managers, e.g. the board of directors or the CEO or those who are responsible for determining the strategic direction of the organization. However, this position can also be held by managers at the middle level, even when needed.

Strategic leadership will greatly help improve company performance and can solve structural problems in an organization. The focus of strategic leadership is not just looking for instant solutions for survival. Strategic leaders must look at the big picture of the company’s future whenever making decisions or implementing changes.

2. The influence of strategic policies on employee performance:

As stated in the hypothesis test, which shows that strategic policies have a significant effect on employee performance, the results of this study support the results of research conducted by Evert Lindquist (2016) that strategic policies are closely related to employee performance. Policy Direction is the formulation of a framework or framework for solving problems and

anticipating issues which will be implemented in stages as a strategy elaboration. The policy direction is the embodiment of a business strategy that is focused on the priorities for achieving company goals.

The policy is a very important aspect, considering its position as a determinant of what is to be done, while what is to be done must be based on certain problems, needs, or aspirations. So it is not true that a policy is decided without any real problems, needs or aspirations and of course, it cannot be based on problems or needs that are created by certain parties to fulfil their interests. Considering that policy is the main concern, the problem and need are the concerns. Therefore, in order for the policy taken to be a solution to various problems, it is necessary to formulate a strategy in formulating the policy.

3. The influence of strategic policies on strategic planning:

The results also show that strategic policies have a significant effect on strategic planning. This supports the previous researcher, namely Alicia Ohlsson (2014), who stated that strategic policies have a significant effect on strategic planning. Planning is one of the management functions that must be carried out by an organization, in addition to other functions, namely organizing, directing and monitoring. Planning is considered as one of the important management functions and has a close relationship with every other management function. This is considering that planning contains everything that is comprehensive as a guide for carrying out all organizational activities. Planning is also often said to be the main management function because it is the basis for all other management functions performed by managers. All plans result in one business plan. Business planning provides one thing that relates to several views of the company's situation today and from other companies and goals.

4. The effect of strategic planning on employee performance:

The statistical test results show that strategic planning has no significant effect on employee performance. The results of this study do not support previous research, including Mizutani and Nakamura (2014); Goldstein and Iossifova (2012); Pitelis (2007), which states that strategic planning, has a significant effect on employee performance. Strategic planning, in particular, is used to sharpen the focus of the organization so that all organizational resources are used optimally to serve the organization's mission.

Strategic planning is a guideline for an organization to be responsive to a dynamic and difficult to predict environment. Strategic planning emphasizes the importance of making decisions that position the organization to respond successfully to a changing environment. The focus of strategic planning is on strategic management, meaning the application of strategic thinking to the task of leading an organization to achieve its goals.

Strategic planning is a company guideline that contains the plans for the future of the company that serves as the achievement of the vision, mission and goals set by the organization. The existence of strategic planning causes the organizational concept to be organized and clear so that it will be easier to determine goals and other plans and can direct

organizational resources effectively and efficiently so that it can be said that strategic planning can determine the success of an organization. So it can be concluded that good performance indicates that the organization has succeeded in achieving the strategy.

5. Strategic planning mediates the influence of strategic leadership on employee performance:

The results of statistical tests have revealed that strategic planning does not mediate the effect of strategic leadership on employee performance. The results of this study do not support the results of previous studies such as Ritta Viitala (2015), which states that strategic planning is the mediator of the relationship between strategic leadership and employee performance. The weakest indicator in reflecting the strategic planning variable is "The leader is always effective and efficient at work" with a factor weight of 0.796 or 79.6%. The weighted factor shows that the respondents expect that the leadership must be effective in realizing the work in the company. Even though this indicator is not the most important for them, they quite feel that the company has implemented effective and efficient work in supporting the work. In fact, this indicator received positive responses from respondents; this is evidenced by the average acquisition above number 4, which is 4.31, which means that many respondents agree and strongly agree. Every company is running its business must be based on various plans that become the foundation and are contained in the company's vision and mission. In preparing a plan, strategic thinking is certainly needed in order to provide a general picture to achieve the strategic plan. Strategic planning can help every organization in the company to achieve the company's long-term goals as a whole. Strategic plans are also used to assess and adjust the company's direction in response to changes in the business environment. At the end of the strategic planning process, the company should have a clear direction in which the business will go in the future. The strategic plan makes the company find out how to develop over the next few years and how to address opportunities and challenges.

6. Strategic planning mediates the effect of strategic policies on employee performance:

The results of this study indicate that strategic planning does not mediate strategic policies on employee performance. Thus the results of this study do not support the results of previous studies such as Trong Tuan Luu (2014), which states that strategic planning is a mediating variable of the influence of strategic leadership on employee performance. A good organization is one that has clear goals based on the vision and mission agreed upon by its founder. To realize these goals, a way to achieve them is needed, which is known as a strategy. Furthermore, plans, policies to achievements and action programs are drawn up. In its application, the above elements may change as a result of not fulfilling the assumptions used in planning, for example, because the resources obtained are not in line with expectations. It could be caused by goals that are too abstract, so it is very far from what is expected. Every organization certainly has a plan for the scope of the company to know the term strategic planning, where this strategic planning can help evaluate periodically to achieve goals, to advance and develop, enlarge market share in the midst of increasingly fierce business competition.

7. Technology capability moderates the influence of strategic leadership on employee performance:

The results of the moderation test show that technological capability moderates the effect of strategic leadership on employee performance. This study supports the findings of previous studies, which state that technological capability moderates the influence of strategic leadership on employee performance (Palladan, Ahmad & Abdulkadir, Kadzrina & Chong, Yen, 2016). It is undeniable that the development of information technology has brought great changes to companies. Information technology has not only changed the way companies conduct business activities but has also changed the company's business perspective and company business processes. To survive in this technological era, of course, companies must also carry out digital transformation. The key to the company's success in carrying out this digital transformation does not only lie in its information technology capabilities but is also influenced by the company's ability to manage and utilize it. The ability to manage information technology is better known as information technology capability. Information technology capability is believed to be able to improve performance for the company, and of course, it is very closely related to company value.

Research findings:

Strategic planning is an important management activity to be implemented properly. In this study, strategic planning has not been able to directly improve employee performance. However, performance increases when strategic leadership with its policies is able to improve performance. In addition, technological capabilities can strengthen leadership with policies when improving employee performance.

Research Implications:

The implications of the research results include theoretical and managerial implications. Theoretical implications are related to the theories of experts through an overview of problem references, models, results and previous research agendas. Managerial implications related to policies that can be related to the findings generated in the study, managerial implications make a practical contribution to management regarding how to improve employee performance in the context of tourism in Jakarta. Good performance must begin with a plan that can be implemented by all employees. The plan is made by the leadership with policies that are basically adjusted by analyzing the characteristics and potential of employees according to their respective expertise in a coordinated manner.

Research Limitations:

For further research that wants to examine strategic leadership in spurring increasingly challenging performance in this digital era, it needs to be developed again in other fields of work and further explore theories and other variables that affect employee performance, for example; organizational characteristics variables, individual characteristics in order to obtain data that is complete knowledge for further research.

CONCLUSION

The results show that strategic leadership is related to employee performance. The most dominant factor in reflecting the strategic leadership variable is "The leader always imitates his subordinates with behaviour. This is approved by employees that it is true that the leader has set an example in his work. Then one of the lowest factors in the strategic leadership variable is "The leader always maintains good relations with subordinates". Although it is the smallest among the other values, in fact, the respondents' level of agreement is quite good. In addition, strategic leadership is also able to improve strategic planning.

Strategic policies can improve employee performance. The highest factor in the strategic policy variable is "Leadership always provides solutions to problems. This has been felt by employees and agreed that leaders often provide solutions at work. The lowest factor in reflecting the strategic policy variable is "Leadership always thinks positively and is customer-focused. This has received approval from employees that it is true that superiors always think positively about problems that arise in the company. Strategic policies are also related to strategic planning, but task planning is not able to improve employee performance. The lowest factor in reflecting employee performance is that I generate a lot of new customers; work results can satisfy customers; I have generated a lot of followers on social media, and the results of my work can satisfy customers. This is the result of employee performance regarding tourism in Jakarta that is not in accordance with the plans that have been made previously.

Strategic planning in this study is not related when strategic leadership improves employee performance. The most important factor in the strategic planning variable is "The leader always thinks about the success of the company" in fact that hope gets approval from employees that the leader is success-oriented.

Strategic planning is also not an important thing in strategic policies in improving employee performance. The weakest factor in reflecting the strategic planning variable is "The leadership is always effective and efficient at work." These results indicate that the respondents expect that the leadership must be effective in realizing the work in the company. Although this factor is not the most important for them, they quite feel that the company has implemented an effective and efficient work system to support tourism in Jakarta.

The results of this study also show that technological capabilities can improve employee performance while strengthening technology capabilities with strategic leadership can improve employee performance which, in the end, technology capabilities have become reinforcements in improving employee performance.

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